
Performance Appraisal and Staff Commitment in Secondary Schools in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study sought to determine the effect of performance appraisal on teacher's commitment in secondary schools' in Calabar Municipality. Specifically, the study explored the effect of goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices and reward system practices on teacher's commitment in secondary school in Calabar Municipality. Three research questions and three null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The study's target population was all teachers and principals in public secondary schools in Calabar Municipality. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique in sample selection. The study sample was 100 respondents. The questionnaire was used to collect primary data. In data analysis, quantitative data were analyzed through descriptive statistics in form of mean and standard deviation using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 26). The study also conducted regression and correlation analysis to test the relationship between the study variables. The study established that secondary school teachers agreed that goal-setting practices have helped them improve teaching methodologies (mean 3.198); The feedback received agrees with what teachers have achieved (mean 3.249); further, the study results revealed a significant positive relationship between goal-setting practices, performance feedback practice as well as reward system practices and teachers' commitment to duty as indicated by the coefficient values of 0.391; 0.279 and 0.277 (with all having a $P < 0.05$), respectively. The study concluded that goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices and reward system practices as a performance appraisal system played a significant role in enhancing teachers' commitment in secondary schools in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State. The study recommended that School supervisors and the ministry of education should enhance goal-setting practices, provide regular and timely feedback to teachers and link attainment of goals with rewards in order to improve as well as sustain teacher's commitment to duty in secondary schools.

Keywords: Feedback, goal-setting, performance appraisal, reward-system, staff commitment.

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Introduction

Secondary schools are expected to prepare students for adulthood making sure that they learn while they are in school and are equipped with skills, they will need to become productive workers and full participants in their societies. The achievement of this important goal depends

on the commitment of the teaching staff which also to a large extent depends on how satisfied they are in respect of school organizations' appraisal mechanism, the extent of participation in decision making as well as career planning strategies. Okeke (2014) after cross-examination of the code of conduct and guidelines for teachers, summarized teachers' effectiveness in secondary schools to include a commitment to the students, commitment to the parents, commitment to the community, commitment to the employer and commitment to the profession.

Staff commitment to duty is an indicator of passion and is essential for high-quality teaching, commitment to the school, students, career continuance, promotion of professional knowledge base and the teaching profession. Staff commitment to the service delivery varies. It can be affective, continuance and normative commitment. The affective commitment involves the teacher's emotional attachment to and involvement with the school and the job. Continuance commitment on the other hand has to do with the perceived costs of leaving the organization, while normative commitment refers to the felt responsibility by the teacher to remain a supportive member of the school. Day (2014) argues that passion for the teaching job is a need for high-quality education. Passion encourages teachers to go the extra mile as it serves as a source of motivation (Vallerand, 2017). Hence, passionate teachers can do all it takes to create excitement for learners to achieve better. Hargreaves in Mustafa (2017) asserted that without passion all pedagogical approaches are bound to fail.

Staff commitment is the bond between the employee and the organization such that the employee wants to continue serving the organization and to help it achieve its objectives (Mugizi, Bakkabulindi & Bisaso, 2015). Staff commitment is important as far organizations such as secondary schools are concerned as it leads to reduced employee turnover because committed employees are loyal to the organization, share its values and identify with the goals of the organization has little reason to want to leave it. As Visagie & Steyn, (2011) puts it, it leads to acceptance of organizational change because when an organization engages in change initiatives, committed employees provide many benefits such as putting in extra effort to ensure that the change succeeds. In addition, during a period of change, committed employees serve as public relations representatives and go beyond the norm to assist the organization to function effectively. Employees with commitment feelings do not frequently involve themselves in negative behaviour such as absenteeism, are more compatible and productive individuals with higher levels of satisfaction, loyalty to the organization.

The low commitment of teachers with no passion for their jobs affects their performance because they hardly take on extra roles in the schools and are less focused on their jobs. They frequently absent themselves from duty and show laxity in teaching. Such teachers experience a reduction in their professional growth and professionalism. Hence, they fail to create effective learning environments and increase the learning potentials of their students (Altun, 2017; Carbonneau, Vallerand, Fernet & Guay, 2008). Therefore, secondary school teachers fail to make schemes of work, lesson plans and performing weekly duty negatively affecting teaching and learning (Ataike, 2014). According to Jonyo and Owuor (2017), ineffective supervision and evaluation systems in public schools have led to teachers' dissatisfaction, lack of

commitment and even teachers' failure to understand the curriculum. One of the key human resources needed for the effective functioning of secondary school education in Nigeria is the teachers. Their commitment to work, however, has a greater contribution to the attainment of the stated goal and objectives of secondary school as enshrined in the National Policy on Education. Ndugu (2011) stated that teachers' performance is reflected on their commitment to duty and further on the academic achievement of the student which is measured by tests scores in various subject areas. Factors such as school infrastructures, professional training, staff development programmes that are provided can influence teachers' commitment and attitude toward work.

In an attempt to ensure that the aims and objectives of education are achieved at a reasonable cost, educational managers have adopted performance appraisal as an integral part of school administration. Teachers' performance appraisal is a method of monitoring and evaluating a teacher's performance at the school level. It involves the setting of performance targets, periodic assessment, feedback on evaluation, performance-based consultations, gathering evidence to demonstrate performance, rating of the performance, identification of performance gaps and planning on teacher development and support measures. Performance appraisal refers to a process, which studies and evaluates the job performance of personnel formally (Mondy, 2008). Cappelli & Conyon (2018) sees performance appraisal as the evaluation of an employee's job performance over the previous period by his/ her supervisor. With performance appraisal, an overall evaluation of work content, loads and volumes is carried out to establish what has been achieved during the reporting period and agree on objectives for the next period (Armstrong, 2010). Performance appraisal offers feedback guidance in a complete system of performance management fostering employee motivation contributing to increased commitment. Santiago & Benavides (2019) concisely captured it thus: as the most important resource in schools, teachers are critical to raising education standards. This is the major reason for which teachers are evaluated seasonally to ensure that they are equipped for imparting quality knowledge relevant for societal enhancement and continuity. As a systematic process, performance appraisal has therefore gained popularity in schools for determining the merit, value, and worth of a teacher's current status and estimating his/her potential level of performance with further development (Mwangi, 2016).

Performance Appraisal is one of the human resource management practices that has been widely studied all over the world and has equally been identified as a strong motivator. Adofo (2011) revealed that performance appraisal is both inevitable and universal because human beings arbitrarily, naturally and formally have a habit of judging themselves and other employee's performance working with them. Such judgments are unlawful and may bring serious problems at the workplace which may affect employees' motivation negatively due to inaccuracies in such judgments. Organizations should have structured performance appraisals to avoid the unfair judgment of their employees. Hyde (2011) in a study revealed far-reaching effects of performance appraisals viz: improving performance, motivating workers, predicting the performance of an individual amongst others. It is through an appraisal that the principal gets a clear framework of activities and responsibilities of each member of staff in the school. An appraisal enables the principal to evaluate the extent to which policies, objectives, activities

and events laid down in the long- and short-term plans are successfully carried out. As a management practice, it offers professional service to secondary school executives to interact and influence teachers to maintain or change and improve their service delivery to the students. It is through an appraisal that teachers are guided and influenced to strive towards the desired educational goals and objectives.

According to Grote (2011), inconsistent and unsuitable performance appraisal will lead to the failure of organizations and poor performance of their employees. Appraising every employee effectively and efficiently will lead to the success of organizations (Kanisa & Makokha 2017). In his work, Agesa (2005) shows the effects of employee appraisal on the performance of teachers. He argues that the appraisal systems should not be used by principals to discriminate against teachers on basis of age, gender, ethnicity political affiliations among others. It becomes pertinent therefore that teachers should be informed of the appraisal tools and the content of the tools. In view of this, it is worthy of note that teachers' commitment is one of the major professional characteristics that influence an educator's success. For the teaching-learning process, teachers' low commitment has an adverse effect on students' behaviour and performance in examinations. It is based on this background that this study is conducted to assess the effect of performance appraisal on staff commitment in secondary schools in Calabar Municipal.

Statement of the problem

Teachers are most times accused of the decline in the standard of education. This, coupled with the fact that some well-performing teachers are often left out when promotions are done has weakened the morale of teachers and their view of the profession. This is evident as many teachers have abandoned their jobs for more profitable ventures while some professionally qualified teachers have abandoned the classroom for more lucrative employments. Several teachers arrive at their respective schools as early as 8:00 am, sign in the attendance book and either disappear or carry out business activities within the school during work hours. It is also observed that the remaining few in the sector are not optimally performing in their jobs to the benefit of the school and the satisfaction of the society. These have had an undesirable effect on performance. Despite the effort of the government towards promoting secondary education, complaints about its falling standards abound and are attributed to poor staff commitment to the teaching job and profession. Hence, the need for this study on the effect of performance appraisal on staff (teachers') commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research objectives

This study aimed to determine the effect of performance appraisal on staff (teachers) commitment in secondary teachers in Calabar Municipal.

The specific objectives of the study include to:

1. To determine the effect of goal setting practices on teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality.

2. To establish the effect of performance feedback practices on teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality.
3. To determine the effect of reward system practices on teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality.

Research questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. What is the effect of goal setting practices on teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality?
2. What is the effect of performance feedback practices on teachers' job commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality?
3. What is the effect of rewards system practices teachers' job commitment secondary schools in Calabar municipality?

Statement of hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between performance appraisal and teachers' commitment to duty in Calabar Municipality.

Literature review

Goal setting practices

Goal setting is seen as fundamental for an organization trying to enhance the likelihood that people and groups will behave in ways that lead to the achievement of organization objectives. Sahai and Srivastava (2012) conducted a study to determine the role of goal setting and performance assessment as a tool for talent management. The study found out that goal setting process creates a more attractive and objective strategy for defining expectations and performance assessment. In conclusion, the study demonstrated that goal setting gives particular and quantifiable objectives thus giving clearness to the workers on what is expected from them. According to the GOK (2009), all types of occupation even the one that is most dull or repetitive their outcomes can be measured. Khan (2014) carried out a study on the effect of goal setting on teachers' performance; the study discovered that goal setting improves teachers' efficiency and effectiveness. In addition, the study discovered that goal setting has a positive effect on work performance. Finally, the study concluded that the goal is imperative to improve the work performance of the teachers because, without goals, workers will not work to their full potential.

Choon and Cheng (2016) conducted a study to research the effect of goal setting on employees' effectiveness to enhance organizational effectiveness in Singapore. The study discovered that goal setting positively affects employee performance and eventually enhances organizational effectiveness. In addition, the study demonstrated that goal is a common idea

that incorporates different concepts like aim, undertaking, deadline, reason, intentions and objective and is deemed as a controller of activity. The study demonstrated that organizations are always looking for methods for accomplishing their goal. The study also revealed that goal setting is viewed as a method for helping all employees to pull in a similar way with a view of increasing performance.

Performance feedback practices

A study conducted by Onyaro (2016), on factors influencing teachers' attitude toward performance. The study revealed that principals do not give feedback on time after appraising the teachers and that the feedback is not communicated in a friendly manner which makes the teachers have a negative attitude toward performance appraisal. The study recommends that feedback should be given immediately after appraising teachers to avoid delays. Odhiambo (2015) carried out a study on the effect of performance management practices on employee productivity: a case study of Schindler Limited found out that effective feedback is essential for any organization to meet its target. In addition, feedback allows the employees to be made aware of what precisely is expected from them. The study also discovered effective performance feedback amongst workers and supervisor is the way to effective strengthening the efficiency of the organization. In conclusion, the study demonstrated that satisfactory feedback builds accountability, since workers and supervisors take an interest in developing goals, recognizing skills, talking about professional advancement and worker motivation.

Kaymaz (2011) conducted a study on performance Feedback on individual-based reflections and the impact in light of motivation. The findings revealed that the performance feedback enhances the behaviour effectiveness of workers which then leads to job motivation. The study also demonstrated that performance feedback impacts motivation by reducing the performance ambiguity, enhancing the manager-subordinate relationship, making it less demanding to accomplish goals, supporting personal development and adjusting to change. The study concluded that performance feedback is an essential source of information that supports the technical and behaviour improvement of all levels in an organization. It is possible to recognize the strengths and shortcomings of the workers with the help of this information. Allube (2015) asserts that providing employees with feedback encourage good performance, strengthens, job-related skills and competencies and help employees keep up with changes in the workplace such as the introduction of new technology or methods.

Rewards system practices

In his study, Odhiambo (2015) revealed that workers are rewarded to meet target productivity levels. In addition, the study indicates that the opportunity by the manager to formally recognize great worker performance prompts work motivation. In conclusion, the study expresses that when great performance is observed and rewarded the chance of it being repeated is increased, while poor performance is demoralized to diminish its possibility of happening once more. Chijioke (2015) revealed that there is a significant relationship between the rewards system and

employees' performance and that there is a noteworthy distinction on the impacts of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards on employee's performance.

Mishra and Ranjan (2017) researched the effect of rewards on workers performance, an instance of Indian oil Corporation, Patna area. The study discovered that cash bonuses have positively affect employee's performance. In any case, a significant number of the employees perceive that it has no positive effect on performance and some of them were impartial. In addition, the study discovered that many employees were not happy with the cash rewards of the organization and bonuses had not been genuinely distributed among the workers. A study conducted by Rowaso (2011) on the effects of a reward system on employee's performance revealed that organizations provide rewards to their employees to try to motivate their performance and encourage their loyalty and retention. The study indicated organizational rewards take several different forms including money (salary, bonuses, and incentive pay), recognition and benefits.

Summary

As a management practice, teachers' performance appraisal helps to monitor and evaluate a teacher's performance at the school level. It involves the setting of performance targets, periodic assessment, feedback on evaluation, performance-based consultations, gathering evidence to demonstrate performance, rating of the performance, identification of performance gaps and planning on teacher development and support measures. Related literature revealed that performance appraisal promotes goal setting, offers feedback guidance and proper reward in a complete system of performance management fostering employee motivation through contributing to increased commitment. An appraisal enables the principal to evaluate the extent to which policies, objectives, activities and events laid down in the long- and short-term plans are successfully carried out. It is through an appraisal that the principal gets a clear framework of activities and responsibilities of each member of staff in the school. However, the review of related literature so far still indicated that although much research has been carried out on performance appraisal and its impact on teachers' performance, no research seems to have been done on the effect of performance appraisal and staff (teachers') work commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality, a gap that the researcher seeks to fill.

Methods

The study adopted a descriptive research design. The choice of this research design will be appropriate for the study that adopts questionnaires as the data collection tool. The study's target population was all teachers and principals in public secondary schools in Calabar Municipals. The study employed a stratified random sampling technique in sample selection. The study sample size was 100 respondents. The questionnaire was used to collect primary data from respondents. The questionnaire contained close-ended questions based on study objectives. The questionnaire employed the five-point Likert scale for standardization of respondents where 1 represents Strongly Disagree 2 represents Disagree 3 represents Neutral 4

represent Agree and 5 represents Strongly Agreed. The instrument was validated and the reliability coefficient (alpha) was 0.70 which was considered acceptable reliability. Data were collected personally by the researcher through the administration of the questionnaire copies to the selected respondent. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the help of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study also used multiple regression analysis to establish the effect of performance appraisal on staff (teachers) commitment in secondary schools in Calabar municipality.

Results

Goal setting practices and teachers' performance

The first objective of the study sought to examine the effect of goal-setting practices on staff (teachers) commitment. The study evaluated the respondents' level of agreement with the various statements on the goal-setting practices using a scale of 1 – 5 where 5- strongly agree, 4- agree, 3- neutral, 2- disagree and 1- strongly disagree. The findings are illustrated in Table 1. The findings, shown in table 1, indicated that the secondary school teachers agreed they set goals at the beginning of every appraisal period the response was 3.266; teachers set an equal number of goals, the response was 3.311; they always achieve the goal set the mean response was 3.147; Setting goal has helped teachers improve my teaching the mean response was 3.198; Goal setting provides clarity to the teachers on what is expected of them 3.282; Setting goals give teachers a sense of direction the response was 2.266; My supervisor regularly discusses my goal with me, the response was 3.226; This implied that goal-setting practices as a performance appraisal system, played an important role in improving the performance of secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality.

Table 1: Respondents' level of agreement with the statement on goal setting practices

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std.
1	Teachers set goals at the beginning of every appraisal period	3.266	0.984
2	Teachers set equal number of goals	3.311	1.142
3	teachers always achieve the goal set	3.147	3.147
4	Setting goal has helped teachers improve my teaching	3.198	0.995
5	Goal setting provides clarity to the teachers on what is expected of them	3.282	1.097
6	Setting goals give teachers a sense of direction	3.266	1.093
7	My supervisor regularly discusses my goal with me	3.226	1.115

Performance feedback practices and teachers' performance

The second objective of the study sought to establish the effect of performance appraisal practices on teacher's commitment in secondary school in Calabar Municipality. The study evaluated the respondents' level of agreement with the various statements on the performance

feedback practices using a scale of 1 – 5 where 5- strongly agree, 4- agree, 3- neutral, 2- disagree and 1- strongly disagree. The findings are as illustrated in Table 2

Table 2: Respondents' level of agreement with statements on performance feedback practices

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Teachers get adequate feedback on my performance based on performance appraisal form	3.158	1.07
2	Teachers always get performance feedback on time	3.181	0.989
3	Supervisor discusses with teachers work performance during appraisal session.	3.192	1.032
4	The feedback received agrees with what teachers have actually Achieved	3.249	1.03
5	Supervisor communicates with teachers frequently on their Work performance	3.203	1.134
6	The performance feedback teachers receive is highly appreciated	3.254	1.07
7	Teachers receive only verbal feedback from their supervisor	3.147	0.994
8	Teachers receive only written feedback from their supervisor	3.288	0.936
9	teachers receive both verbal and written feedback from their supervisor	3.198	3.197

The findings shown in table 2 above indicated that the secondary school teachers agreed they get adequate feedback on performance based on performance appraisal form, the mean response was 3.254; teachers always get performance feedback on time the mean response was 3.181; Supervisor discusses with teachers work performance during appraisal session, the mean response was 3.192; The feedback received agrees with what teachers have achieved, the mean response was 3.249; Supervisor communicates with teachers frequently on their work performance the mean response was 3.203; the performance feedback teachers receive is highly appreciated, the mean response was 3.158; teachers receive only verbal feedback from their supervisor, the mean response was 3.147; teachers receive only written feedback from my supervisor the mean response was 3.288; teachers receive both verbal and written feedback from my supervisor, the mean response was 3.198. This implied that a performance feedback practice as a performance appraisal system was critical in improving the performance of secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipal.

Reward system practices and teachers' performance

The last objective of the study sought to establish the effect of reward system practices on the performance of secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality. The study evaluated the respondents' level of agreement with the various statements on the reward system practices using a scale of 1 – 5 where 5- strongly agree, 4- agree, 3- neutral, 2- disagree and 1- strongly disagree. The findings are illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Respondents' level of agreement with statements on reward system practices

S/N	Statement	Mean	SD
1	Salary paid to teachers is adequate	3.616	0.999
2	When teachers, work contribution is recognized by the supervisor they feel motivated	3.785	0.852
3	Opportunities for further studies encourage teachers to put more effort	3.249	1.1
4	Ministry of education provide teachers with opportunity for career advancement	3.266	0.955
5	Ministry of education pegs promotion on work performance	3.158	1.101
6	Ministry of education links work performance with reward	3.192	0.987
7	I have been promoted more than once since I joined teaching profession	3.305	0.883

From the findings shown in table 3 above, the secondary school teachers agreed that salary paid to them is adequate, the mean response was 3.616; when teachers, work contribution is recognized by the supervisor they feel motivated the mean response was 3.785; opportunities for further studies encourage teachers to put more effort, the mean response was 3.249, ministry of education provides teachers with an opportunity for career advancement, the mean response was 3.266; ministry of education pegs promotion on work performance the mean response was 3.158; ministry of education links work performance with rewards, the mean response was 3.192; I have been promoted more than once since I joined teaching profession the mean response was 3.305. This implied that reward system practices as performance appraisal systems are integral in improving teachers' commitment in the secondary schools' system in Calabar municipality.

Hypothesis

The study conducted a regression analysis to explore the relationship between the variables of the study. This was performed by regressing the independent variable (goal-setting setting, performance feedback practices and reward system practices) against the dependent variable (teachers' commitment). The results are summarized in Table 4. According to table 4 above R square was 0.755 which means 75.5% variation in teachers' performance was due to goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices and reward system practices while the remaining 24.5% of the variation in teachers' performance was explained by other factors not considered in the study. The F test was significant with a p-value =0.000 which was less than the standard p-value of 0.05 and this meant that the model was significant. From ANOVA, since the p-value was 0.000 and was less than the p-value of 0.05 (p-value 0.000<0.05), then the effect of goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices and reward system practices affect the teacher's commitment to duty.

From the regression equation above, taking all factors (goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices and reward system practices) constant at zero, the performance of teachers would be 0.387. The results further indicate that a unit increase in the goal-setting practice would lead to a 0.391 increase in the performance of secondary teachers; a unit increase

in performance feedback practices would lead to a 0.279 increase in performance of secondary teachers while a unit increase in reward system practices would lead to a 0.227 increase in performance of secondary teachers. At the 5% significance level [or 95% level of confidence], goal-setting practices had a 0.00 level of significance; performance feedback had a 0.002 level of significance while the reward system had a 0.001 level of significance. All the variables were significant ($p < 0.05$) with the most significant factor being goal-setting practices followed by reward system practices and performance feedback.

Table 4: Model summary

Model Summary					
R	R ²		Adj. R ²	SE	
0.869	0.755		0.751	0.383	
ANOVA					
Model	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	78.616	3	26.205	178.059	.000
Residual	104.076	173	0.147		
Total	25.461	176			
Relative coefficients					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	SE	Beta	t	
(Constant)	0.387	0.177		2.182	.030
Goal-setting practices (X1)	0.391	0.088	0.448	4.464	.000
Performance feedback (X2)	0.279	0.089	0.319	3.124	.002
Reward system practices (X3)	0.227	0.068	0.165	3.319	.001

Based on the regression results shown on table 4, the regression model fitted is as:

$$Y = 0.387 + 0.391X_1 + 0.297X_2 + 0.227X_3 \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Discussion

The study findings showed the secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality did agree that they set goals at beginning of every appraisal period; they set equal numbers of goals: they always achieve the goal set; setting goals has helped them improve the teaching methodologies; setting goal provide clarity on what is expected of them; setting goal gives a sense of direction and their supervisor regularly discuss their goal with them. This implied that goal-setting practices as a performance appraisal system played a significant role in enhancing teacher's commitment in the study area. The finding is in line with the study carried out by Khan (2014) on the effect of goal setting on teachers' performance; the study discovered that goal setting improves teachers' efficiency and effectiveness. In addition, the study discovered that goal setting has a positive effect on work performance.

On the issue of performance feedback, the research findings showed that the secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality did agree that they get adequate feedback on their performance based on performance appraisal form; they always get feedback on time; their supervisor discusses with them work performance during appraisal session; the feedback they

receive agrees with what they have achieved; supervisor communicates with them frequently on work performance; the feedback they receive on how they perform their job is highly appreciated and that they receive both verbal and written performance feedback. This implied that feedback practices as a performance appraisal system were integral in efforts to improve teacher's commitment to duty in Calabar Municipality. The findings of the study correspond to those of (Allube, 2015) who asserts that providing employees with feedback encourage good performance, strengthens, job-related skills and competencies and help employees keep up with changes in the workplace such as the introduction of new technology or methods.

The study findings further showed that the secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality did agree that they feel motivated when their work contribution is recognized; opportunity for further studies encourage them to put more effort; ministry of education provides teachers with an opportunity for career advancement; ministry of education pegs promotion on work performance and that they link work performance with rewards. This implied that the reward system as a performance appraisal system played a crucial role in enhancing the commitment of secondary school teachers in Calabar Municipality. The findings concurred with Chijioke (2015) who revealed that there is a significant relationship between rewards system and employees' performance and that there is a noteworthy distinction on the impacts of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards on employee's performance.

Further, the regression analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices as well as reward system practices and teachers' commitment to work as indicated by Beta values 0.391; 0.279 and 0.227 (with all having $p < 0.05$), respectively. This agreed with Muli (2012) who revealed that appropriate appraisal schemes have the potential to improve the professionalization of teaching, the effective management of schools, the quality of education provided for the students, the professional development of teachers as well as satisfying legitimate demands for accountability.

Conclusion

This study was conducted to investigate the effect of performance appraisal on staff commitment in secondary schools' in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State, Nigeria. The study concluded that goal-setting practices, performance feedback practices, and reward system practices as a performance appraisal system played a significant role in enhancing teacher's commitment to duty in secondary school in Calabar municipality. The study also concluded that there existed a significant positive relationship between performance feedback practices, goal-setting practices, reward system practices and teacher's commitment in secondary school in Calabar municipality.

Recommendations

School supervisors and the ministry of education should enhance goal-setting practices, provide regular and timely feedback to teachers and link attainment of goals with rewards in order to improve as well as sustain teacher's commitment to duty in secondary schools.

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